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HONORARIUM GUIDANCE FOR INVOLVEMENT ACTIVITIES IN RESEARCH PROJECTS

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Citizens, people with relevant lived experience and professional expertise (e.g. patients and their family members, practitioners, and subject-matter experts), as well as stakeholder groups (e.g. non-profit organisations (NPOs/NGOs), associations, public authorities, companies, and health or educational institutions), can be actively involved in research in many different ways. This approach recognises that scientific, professional, and experiential knowledge all provide valuable contributions to research. For example, contributors may advise researchers through advisory boards or steering groups during the planning of research projects, work alongside researchers as equal partners to identify research priorities and formulate research questions, contribute to the design of the research, co-develop project information and study materials, collect, analyse, and interpret data, or support the dissemination of research findings to wider audiences. Further information and practical guidance on involving citizens, people affected by research, and stakeholder groups can be found in [Kaisler & Missbach \(2019\)](#) and [Wellcome](#).

As a recognition of the valuable contributions made by those involved in research projects, the LBG OIS Center recommends providing appropriate honoraria. Accepting an honorarium is entirely voluntary. Alternatively, non-monetary forms of recognition or compensation (e.g. vouchers, group activities, or language courses) may be agreed upon. Participants may also choose to donate all or part of their honorarium. Depending on an individual's circumstances, alternative forms of compensation may be more appropriate, particularly for self-employed individuals, people receiving means-tested social benefits, or those without a bank account. To avoid misunderstandings and administrative challenges, project leaders are encouraged to communicate openly and transparently about the type, amount, and payment arrangements before participants become actively involved in the project.

In addition to any honorarium, participants may be reimbursed for travel expenses, meals, childcare, personal assistance or support persons, and other necessary costs incurred through their involvement. Researchers should also ensure that involvement activities are as accessible as possible and that individual support needs are considered from the outset, enabling people with diverse backgrounds, abilities, and circumstances to participate on an equal basis.

The following recommended honorarium rates provide guidance for compensating citizens, people with lived experience, and other practice partners who actively contribute to research projects. The appropriate level of compensation should reflect the time commitment involved, the preparation and follow-up required, the level of responsibility assumed, and the nature and complexity of the contribution.

EUR 20

For short tasks or activities lasting less than 30 minutes and requiring little or no preparation, for example reviewing and commenting on short documents or providing feedback on project materials.

EUR 40

For tasks or activities lasting approximately one hour and requiring little or no preparation, for example participating in a focus group or interview to provide feedback on a project idea or research materials.

EUR 80

For tasks or activities lasting up to two hours that require some preparation, for example participating in a meeting or teleconference for which documents need to be reviewed in advance.

EUR 120

For activities lasting approximately half a day that require active participation and appropriate preparation, for example participating in workshops, advisory boards, steering groups, or selection panels.

EUR 240

For full-day workshops, meetings, or events requiring active participation and collaboration, for example serving on an advisory board or steering group, participating in co-creation workshops, or contributing to other participatory research activities.

EUR 360

For full-day activities requiring substantial preparation or additional responsibility, for example co-facilitating or facilitating a workshop, co-delivering training, or taking on an active role in planning and delivering participatory processes.

EUR 480–600

For full-day activities involving substantial preparation, a high level of responsibility, and decision-making authority, for example serving on funding or selection panels, reviewing research proposals, or taking on a leadership role in strategic decision-making processes.

These amounts are intended as recommended guideline rates and may be adjusted depending on the project context, the scope of the activity, the level of expertise required, and the individual circumstances of those involved. Clear and transparent communication about the type and amount of the honorarium before collaboration begins is essential for ensuring fair, respectful, and meaningful involvement.